

The Photochemical Reaction between Sodium Nitrite and Iodine.

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This reaction is very sensitive to light and has been investigated in detail in these laboratories (Banerji and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 172; Mukerji and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 850). The velocity of the reaction has been followed by measuring the changes in the concentration of iodine against thiosulphate solution. Recently Berthoud and Berger (*J. Chim. phys.*, 1928, 25, 562) has shown that nitrite and iodine react more readily in presence of sodium thiosulphate solution and consequently the estimation of iodine by thiosulphate leads to erroneous results.

In this communication we are submitting the results obtained in the determination of the order, temperature coefficient and quantum efficiency of this reaction in light of different wave-lengths. We have determined the changes in the concentration of iodine by a Nutting's spectrophotometer.

The reaction can be represented by the equation :

The influence of the variation of intensity of the incident radiation has been investigated in different radiations and using different amounts of potassium iodide, which is a marked retarder. Both sodium acetate and borax solutions have been used as buffer solutions.

Kinetics and Quantum Efficiency.

The source of light and the experimental arrangement are the same as described in a previous paper (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 176, 372).

The following are the experimental results :—

2/8 N-Sodium nitrite = 5 c. c.; N/82-iodine in N/8·2-potassium iodide = 10 c. c., in presence of 5 c. c. N/6·25-sodium acetate.

Condition.	Temperature.	Monomolecular k_1 .	Semi-molecular $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$. After deducting the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff.	Temp. coeff. after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
Dark	30°	0·00819		2·7		
		$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 0·0090				
	40°	0·00866		2·61		
		$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 0·0241				
	50°	0·02260				
		$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 0·0537				
N/8-NaNO ₂	30°	0·00162		2·59		
	40°	0·00419		2·49		
	50°	0·0104				

Hence the order of the reaction is bimolecular in the dark.

$\lambda = 4725\text{Å}$	30°	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ 0·0251	0·0161			5·15 × 10
	40°	0·0575	0·0334		2·07	8·6 ..
	50°	0·1207	0·0870		2·0	11·9 ..
$\lambda = 5650\text{Å}$	30°	0·0212	0·0122			3·94 ..
	40°	0·0510	0·0269		2·2	6·8 ..
	50°	0·111	0·0563		2·1	10·2 ..
$\lambda = 7804\text{Å}$	30°	0·0186	0·0196			8·8 ..
	40°	0·0461	0·0220		2·29	6·2 ..
	50°	0·101	0·0473		2·15	8·1 ..
$\lambda = 8500\text{Å}$	30°	0·0147	0·0057			3·6 ..
	40°	0·0375	0·0134		2·35	5·2 ..
	50°	0·0835	0·0298		2·20	7·3 ..

From the foregoing results it will be observed that Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence is not exactly applicable to this reaction. The quantum efficiency increases with temperature and the frequency of the incident radiation. Similar results have been obtained with numerous other reactions.

The experimental results show that the temperature coefficients of the photochemical changes are less than those of the corresponding thermal reactions. The greater the acceleration in light of different wave-lengths, the less the temperature coefficient. Another

interesting fact is that the temperature coefficient of the purely light reaction is much greater than unity. Similar results have been obtained with several other reactions so far investigated in these laboratories. Hence we are in a position to uphold our view that the temperature coefficient of photochemical reactions need not be unity and depends on the acceleration of the light reaction in comparison with the dark reaction (compare Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707). Many people believe that the photochemical reactions are brought about by violet and ultra-violet radiations only. Our experimental results, however, prove that this and several other reactions can be accelerated by radiations of wave-length 7304 Å and 8500 Å which lie in the infra-red region of the spectrum. Moreover, we have shown that these radiations are actually absorbed by the reacting substances.

Relation between Absorption of Light and Velocity.

The experimental arrangements are the same as described in previous paper (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 175 375).

The corresponding dark reaction was always subtracted from the light reaction before calculating the effect of intensity of light on the velocity of this reaction.

The following are the experimental results :—2/3N-sodium nitrite=5 c. c. ; N-92-iodine in presence of 5 c. c. 6·25N-sodium acetate=10 c. c. Temperature=40°.

Diameter of the aperture.	Semi-molecular. $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Semi-molecular reaction in light after deducting the dark reaction $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
	A. Source.—Sunlight. $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (dark)=0·0241	
2 cm.	0·256	0·2319 (I)
0·8	0·169	0·1449 (II)
0·4	0·148	0·119 (III)
	B. Source.—1000-watt lamp.	
2	0·0866	0·0845 (I)
0·8	0·0556	0·0516 (II)
0·4	0·0416	0·0176 (III)

Diameter of the aperture.	Semi-molecular. $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$	Semi-molecular reaction in light after deducting the dark reaction $k_{\frac{1}{2}}$.
C. Region.— $\lambda=5650\text{\AA}$		
2 cm.	0.0460	0.0219 (I)
0.8	0.0296	0.0066 (II)
0.4	0.0259	0.0018 (III)
D. Region.— $\lambda=7304\text{\AA}$		
2	0.0420	0.0179 (I)
0.8	0.0277	0.0086 (II)
0.4	0.0251	0.0010 (III)
E. Region.— $\lambda=7304\text{\AA}$		

$N/8\frac{1}{2}$ —Iodine dissolved in 0.75 g. KI in presence of
 $N/105$ -borax solution.

		$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (dark) = 0.0450
2	0.0592	0.0142
0.8	0.0471	0.0021

The following results show that the absorption of radiation is approximately proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation. Temperature = 40°.

Diameter of the aperture.	Substance.	Deflection.	Difference in deflection.
2 cm.	(i) Distilled water	38.6 cm.	3.6 cm.
	(ii) Reacting mixture	35.0	
0.8	(i) Distilled water	21.2	0.6
	(ii) Reacting mixture	20.6	
0.4	(i) Distilled water	12.65	0.15
	(ii) Reacting mixture	12.5	

Ratio of intensity.

$$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$$

$$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$$

$$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$$

Ratio of absorption.

$$\frac{3.6}{0.6} = 6$$

$$\frac{0.6}{0.15} = 4$$

$$\frac{3.6}{0.15} = 24$$

Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to the absorption of incident radiation.	If proportional to the square root of the absorption of incident radiation.
A. $\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.2319}{0.1449} = 1.6$	6	2.45
$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.1449}{0.119} = 1.22$	4	2
$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.2319}{0.119} = 1.95$	24	4.9
B. $\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0645}{0.0315} = 2.05$	6	2.45
$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0315}{0.0175} = 1.8$	4	2
$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0645}{0.0175} = 3.7$	24	4.9
C. $\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0219}{0.0055} = 4$	6	2.45
$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0055}{0.0018} = 3$	4	2
$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0219}{0.0018} = 12$	24	4.9
D. $\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0179}{0.0036} = 5$	6	2.45
$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0036}{0.0010} = 3.6$	4	2
$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0179}{0.0010} = 17.9$	24	4.9
E. $\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0142}{0.0021} = 6$	6	2.45

Discussion.

The experimental results show that the relation between the absorption or intensity and the velocity of the reaction varies from approximately one-fourth to more than proportional. Hence it is clear that the relation between light absorption or intensity, and

velocity of one and the same reaction can be varied considerably. It depends entirely on the ratio of the velocities of the light and dark reactions.

When the velocity of the thermal reaction is less and the reaction mixture is exposed to sunlight, the relation between light absorption or intensity and the velocity tends to be less than 1/3. This relation goes on increasing as the acceleration of the light reaction over the corresponding thermal reaction is decreased. It increased so much as to show a relation approximately 3/2 in the region $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$ using $N/105$ -borax solution as a buffer solution, which markedly accelerates the dark reaction. The source of light is not intense in this case. The total result is that the acceleration due to light is not marked in comparison with the dark reaction and the ratio between light absorption or intensity and velocity rises approximately to 3/2.

These results are in entire agreement with our conclusions that the reaction between light absorption or intensity and velocity of a reaction can be varied considerably and is controlled by the ratio of the light and dark reactions.

The Influence of Sodium Nitrite on the amount of Sodium Thiosulphate necessary to react with Iodine.

The following are the experimental results:— $\text{NaNO}_2 = N/5 +$
Iodine = $N/10$ (approximately). Sodium thiosulphate = $N/10$.

Vol. of iodine solution	...	10 c.c.	10 c.c.	10 c.c.	10 c.c.
Vol. of nitrite solution	...	Nil	10	20	30
Vol. of thiosulphate solution	...	9.65	8.55	6.90	6.50

Hence the titration by sodium thiosulphate is vitiated only by concentrated solutions of sodium nitrite. With the concentrations used by Banerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*), the experimental results appear not to be vitiated by the induced reaction between nitrite and iodine due to the interaction of the latter with sodium thiosulphate.

Moreover, the results obtained in this communication using a Nutting's spectrophotometer, are in agreement with those obtained by Banerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) and Mukerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*).

We are at present investigating this reaction in ultra-violet radiations and the equilibrium involved in the oxidation of nitrite ion to nitrate ion by iodine.

Summary.

1. The reaction between sodium nitrite and iodine is bimolecular in the dark. The temperature coefficient of the dark reaction is 2.7 between 30° and 40°.

2. The temperature coefficients of the light reaction are 2.07 ($\lambda = 4725\text{\AA}$), 2.20 ($\lambda = 5650\text{\AA}$), 2.29 ($\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$), 2.35 ($\lambda = 8500\text{\AA}$) between 30° and 40°.

3. The quantum efficiency of this reaction varies from 3.6×10 to 11.9×10 at different temperatures and in different radiations.

4. The ratio of light absorption or intensity of the incident radiation and the velocity of the reaction can vary from approximately one-fourth to more than proportional depending on the ratio of the velocities of the light and dark reactions.

5. The titration of iodine by sodium thiosulphate in presence of sodium nitrite is only erroneous when the concentration of sodium nitrite solution is great.

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